

Giant exchange bias in $\text{Zn}_{0.3}\text{Ni}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ system

Rajendra Mohan, Mritunjoy Prasad Ghosh, Samrat Mukherjee*

Department of Physics,

National Institute Of Technology, Patna, India

* samrat.udc@gmail.com, 9973791523

Abstract

Exchange bias (eb) is an induced magnetic anisotropy. It is generally observed when ferromagnetic (FM)/antiferromagnetic (AFM) interfaces are cooled through the Neel temperature (T_N) of the AFM component. These EB systems have promising applications in the field of magnetic recording, spin valves, permanent magnets etc. The hysteresis loop for an EB system when cooled through T_N in the presence of magnetic field, shifts along the field axis in the direction opposite to the cooling field (1-3). We have investigated the EB effects for Zn substituted Ni-ferrite with a specific composition of $\text{Zn}_{0.3}\text{Ni}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$. X-ray diffraction and transmission electron microscopy confirmed the phase-purity and particle size of the samples. Our principal aim was to observe EB by observing the interaction between the surface and core of single-phase magnetic nanoparticles.

Exchange bias, magnetic anisotropy

References

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